

Non-State Actors, Climate Litigation and the Shaping of the Energy Transition

ARQUS Twinning Local Energy Transition

Climate Justice in a Climate-Constrained World!
Non-State Actors, Climate Litigation and the Shaping
of the Energy Transition

Aubin Nzaou-Kongo, PhD

University of Bergen
University of Lyon, Jean Moulin Lyon 3
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arQus

European University Alliance

**How do Non-State Actors - as local Players -
Push for Climate Justice in the Energy
Transition?**

Who are the Non-State Actors?

Who are the Non-State Actors?

Groups/Organisations/etc.

Who are the Non-State Actors?

Individuals

Who are the Non-State Actors?

Major Groups

Individuals

Who are the Non-State Actors?

Major Groups

(Private [For Profit/Non-Profit] & Public)

Children and
Youth (25)

Farmers
Groups (32)

Indigenous
People and
Communities
(26)

Non-
Governmental
Organizations
(27)

Non-Profit
Organizations
(?)

Local
Authorities'
Initiatives
(28)

Workers and
Trade Unions
(29)

Scientific and
Technological
Community
(31)

Business and
Industry (30)

Individuals

Women (24)

Men (?)

*AGENDA 21
United Nations Conference on
Environment & Development
Rio de Janeiro, Brazil,
3-14 June 1992*

What do they do?

What do they do?

Common Good ?

Social Issues

What do they do?

Common Good ?

Environmental Issues

What do they do?

Common Good ?

Economic Issues

What do they do?

Common Good ?

Environmental

Economic

Social

Justice

Do they consider that we live in a Climate-Constrained World?

Non-State Actors Resort to Climate Litigation around the World

Number of cases

Note: The data is current as of 1 July 2020.

The Latest Scientific and Technical Reports confirm the Situation of Constraint

Climate Change 2022

Emissions Gap Report 2021

Global Environment Outlook

The Climate-Constrained World in a Few Words

The Emissions Gap Report 2021 shows that new national climate pledges combined with other mitigation measures put the world on track for a global temperature rise of 2.7°C by the end of the century. That is well above the goals of the Paris climate agreement and would lead to catastrophic changes in the Earth's climate. To keep global warming below 1.5°C this century, the aspirational goal of the Paris Agreement, the world needs to halve annual greenhouse gas emissions in the next eight years.

If implemented effectively, net-zero emissions pledges could limit warming to 2.2°C, closer to the well-below 2°C goal of the Paris Agreement. However, many national climate plans delay action until after 2030.

The Heat Is On
A world of climate promises
not yet delivered

UN environment programme | 50 1972-2022 | UNEP DTU PARTNERSHIP

Emissions Gap Report 2021

**Climate Litigation Could Be a Tremendous
Leverage**

**It Can Change the Course of Things
Based on the Binding Nature of Judicial
Judgements/Decisions**

So, what is Climate Litigation?

Climate Litigation => Cases involving fact-based questions of law or policy relating to climate change mitigation, adaptation, climate change science, the climate system, or any other climate-related issue. => **Ratione Materiae Approach**

Climate Litigation => Cases involving public or private actors/players which refer to obligations to do or not to do, the consequences of which are deemed harmful in the face of the climate emergency => **Ratione Personae Approach**

Climate Litigation Trends

Climate Rights

—Union of Swiss Senior Women for Climate Protection v. Swiss Federal Council
—Greenpeace Nordic Ass'n and Nature & Youth v. Ministry of Petroleum and Energy
—Inter-American Court of Human Rights issued Advisory Opinion OC-23/17
—Urgenda, the Supreme Court of the Netherlands
—ENVironnement JEUnesse v. Canada
—Kim Yujin et al. v. South Korea

Domestic Law and Climate

—Thomson v. Minister for Climate Change Issues
—VZW Klimatzaak v. Kingdom of Belgium
—Friends of the Irish Environment CLG v. Gov't of Ireland
—Mataatua District Maori Council v. New Zealand
—Sheikh Asim Farooq v. Federation of Pakistan
—Ecology Action et al. v. Minister of Environment and Climate Change

Fossil Fuel and Climate

—Plan B Earth, Gloucester Resources Limited, and Ecology Action
—Private Corporation for the Development of Aysen, et al. v. Environmental Evaluation Service of Chile
—Save Lamu et al. v. National Environmental Management Authority and Amu Power Co. Ltd
WildEarth
Guardians v. U.S.

Corporate Liability and Climate Change

—Lliuya v. RWE AG
—Smith v. Fronterra Co-Operative Group Limited

Climate Change Adaptation

Ralph Lauren 57 v. Byron Shire Council
Conservation Law Foundation v. ExxonMobil
Burgess v. Ontario Minister of Natural Resources and Forestry
Philippi Horticultural Area Food & Farming Campaign v. MEC for Local Government, Environmental

So, Climate Justice!

Are Environmental Justice and Climate Justice Correlated?

A Little Background

Environmental Justice: Origin = Difficult to Trace => but associated with the Environmental Justice Movement in the US

Triggering Factor: in 1982 Protests in Warren County, North Carolina => starting point of the Environmental Justice Movement

(Robert D. Bullard, *Confronting Environmental Racism*, South End Press, 1993, at 3.)

A rural and poor area, where the majority of black Americans lived, had been chosen by the authorities to serve as a polychlorinated biphenyl (PCB) dump. This unwise choice had led to a vast demonstration leading to the arrest of a little more than 500 demonstrators. The American civil rights movement used the term "environmental racism," which expressed the idea that after two centuries of slavery, colonization and segregation, black Americans were disproportionately subjected to industrial and chemical pollution and toxic waste.

(Eileen Gauna, "Environmental Law, Civil Rights and Sustainability: Three Frameworks for Environmental Justice," 19 J. Envtl. & Sustainability L. 34 (2012), at 37).

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A Little Background

It appeared to civil rights actors that the decision about the landfill was primarily about making one social group, black Americans in extreme poverty, pay the price for pollution because they were powerless and could not resist/protest/react.

(Robert D. Bullard, [1990], *Dumping in Dixie: Race, Class, and Environmental Quality*, 3rd ed. Boulder, CO: Westview Press).

The term "**environmental racism**" coined by **Benjamin Chavis** (*Benjamin F. Chavis, Commission for Racial Justice United Church of Christ, Toxic Wastes and Race in The United States: a National Report on Racial and Socio-Economic Characteristics of Communities with Hazardous Waste Sites, ix-x (1987) [hereinafter toxic wastes and race]*) had been **hotly contested** because of the **nuance needed between racist intent and implicit bias**

(Richard J. Lazarus, "Environmental Racism! That's What It Is," 2000 U. ILL. L. REv. 255, 259 (2000)).

So, Climate Justice!

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From then on, it was at the **First National People of Color Environmental Leadership Summit**, bringing together just over **50 delegations of civil society organizations** in Washington D.C. in **1991**, that the **principles of environmental justice were adopted** (Clifford Rechtschaffen, Eileen Gauna & Catherine O'Neill, *Environmental Justice: Law, Policy & Environmental Regulation*, 24 (2d ed. 2009)).

These principles emphasized the **environmental justice movement** as the **appropriate framework for reconciling environmental protection and social justice** (Stingl A.I. (2021) Climate Justice. In: Leal Filho W., Marisa Azul A., Brandli L., Lange Salvia A., Özuyar P.G., Wall T. (eds) *Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions. Encyclopedia of the UN Sustainable Development Goals*. Springer, Cham).

“The concept of **environmental justice** is **closely tied to sustainable development**, but refines it with the proposition that **people of color and low-income communities** should **neither bear a disproportionate share of environmental burdens** nor be **disproportionately deprived of environmental benefits**”

Uma Outka, “Environmental Justice Issues in Sustainable Development: Environmental Justice in the Renewable Energy Transition,” 19 *J. Env'tl. & Sustainability L.* 60 (2012)).

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Question

Is it fair to say that climate justice is about ensuring that low-income communities do not bear a disproportionate share of the climate burden and are not disproportionately deprived of the benefits of climate action?

Leghari v. Federation of Pakistan

Leghari: agriculturist and a citizen of Pakistan=> filed a case (on the grounds of public interest litigation)= challenged the inaction, delay and lack of seriousness on the part of the Federal Government and the Government of the Punjab to address the challenges and to meet the vulnerabilities associated with Climate Change in Pakistan.

Public interest litigation: allows entertainment of litigation from socially-disadvantaged parties

Claim: Federal Climate Initiatives (National Climate Change Policy [2012] and the Framework for Implementation of Climate Change Policy [2014-2030]) = Not implemented on the ground

Petition filed on the grounds of fundamental rights: Right to life (art. 9 Constitution) + Right to healthy environment and right to human dignity (art. 14)

Scheme

Violation of rights due to CC+Based on scientific evidence+Connection to reality on the ground in Pakistan+CC caused by human activities+Constitute threat to livelihood+State should take action=did nothing

**The Lahore High Court Lahore Judicial
Department
Ord. 04.09.2015/
Confirmed Judgement 25.01.2018**

***The need to protect the human rights of the disadvantaged people: Climate Justice**

“Climate Change is a defining challenge of our time and has led to dramatic alterations in our planet’s climate system (Climate Change as a defining challenge). For Pakistan, these climatic variations have primarily resulted in heavy floods and droughts, raising serious concerns regarding water and food security. On a legal and constitutional plane this is clarion call for the protection of fundamental rights of the citizens of Pakistan, in particular, the vulnerable and weak segments of the society who are unable to approach this Court (Climate Justice).” (Para. 6)

“Fundamental rights, like the right to life (article 9) which includes the right to a healthy and clean environment and right to human dignity (article 14) read with constitutional principles of democracy, equality, social, economic and political justice include within their ambit and commitment, the international environmental principles of sustainable development, precautionary principle, environmental impact assessment, inter and intra-generational equity and public trust doctrine ” (Para. 7)

**The Lahore High Court Lahore Judicial
Department
Ord. 04.09.2015/
Confirmed Judgement 25.01.2018**

***Environmental Justice connected to Climate Justice: but Climate Justice
=> Correlation Fundamental Rights + Climate Change + Environment
Necessity of fashioning environmental case-law promoting Climate Justice**

“Environment and its protection has taken a center stage in the scheme of our constitutional rights. It appears that we have to move on. The existing environmental jurisprudence has to be fashioned to meet the needs of something more urgent and overpowering i.e., Climate Change. From Environmental Justice, which was largely localized and limited to our own ecosystems and biodiversity, we need to move to Climate Change Justice. Fundamental rights lay at the foundation of these two overlapping justice systems. Right to life, right to human dignity, right to property and right to information under articles 9, 14, 23 and 19A of the Constitution read with the constitutional values of political, economic and social justice provide the necessary judicial toolkit to address and monitor the Government’s response to climate change.” (Para. 7)

“In the present case, the delay and lethargy of the State in implementing the Framework offends the fundamental rights of the citizens which need to be safeguarded.” (Para. 7)

Company Workers Union of Maritima & Commercial Somarco Limited and Others v Ministry of Energy

In 2019, in order to reach the **goal of carbon neutrality by 2050**, the Ministry of Energy of Chile negotiated an agreement with the energy companies involved in decarbonization process: phase-out coal-fired thermoelectric power plants => Coal power plants accounted for 36.7% of energy generation in 2019 [25% of greenhouse gas emissions]

Energy Sector Decarbonization Plan=> gradual closure of existing coal-fired power plants at the national level

A Just Energy Transition Strategy was designed: reintegration of Coal power plant workers into the workforce + safeguard their rights

In 2020, the Ministry of Energy issued the Decree No. 42=> implementation of the plan without consulting with targeted workers

On 26 March 2021, 3 Union Workers filed a petition against the Ministry of Energy

Claim: not consulted in the energy decarbonization agreements or during processes

In violation of their constitutional rights (Article 19) Right to Equality before the Law, Freedom of Labor, Freedom of Association, and Property Rights

The Supreme Court of Chile

9 August 2021

***Social Cost of the Transition: workers and the communities affected**

“That the implementation of the so-called **"Just Transition"** proposal, promoted by the Departments of Energy, Labor and Environment, together with other actors, is specifically aimed at addressing the effects of the exit from coal-fired generation, in order to achieve a just and equitable transformation process, both for the workers affected by the loss of their direct and indirect source of employment and therefore of their income, and for the communities affected by the loss of services linked to the development of the declining thermoelectric activity, thus combining environmental, economic and social development.” (Para. 8) [***No Energy Transition at the Expense of People’s Rights**]

However, it is precisely on this point that the petitioners challenge the respondent's activity, because, although the challenged measure is the **"cornerstone"** of the decarbonization process at the national level, the rights of workers in the coal-fired power industry are at risk due to their exclusion from the development of the strategy for a just energy transition, ignoring their status as dependents who suffer a loss, in the transition to cleaner energy production, generally associated with the loss of jobs in the locations of the disappearing thermoelectric plants.

That, likewise, it is important to emphasize that in such situations, faced with such definitive determinations for individuals, greater diligence must be demanded of the authority, which must act ex officio and respect the principles of non-discrimination, objectivity and completeness in its actions.” (Para. 10)

The Supreme Court of Chile

9 August 2021

[*No Energy Transition based on Discrimination]

“That, therefore, it is found that the actions of the defendant authority involved the exercise of a power, but, ignoring, without more, the imperative need to adopt early measures to avoid the pernicious consequences that a specific group of workers was faced, due to the decarbonization project being developed, especially if, as in this case, guarantees mainly protected by the constitution, such as the right to work, are involved.” (Para. 11)

[*No Energy Transition if Fundamental Rights are not Safeguarded]

In view of these considerations, and also in accordance with the provisions of **article 20 of the Constitution** of the Republic and the decree of this Court on the matter, the contested judgment of March 26 of this year is revoked, and in its place it is declared that **the appeal for protection is accepted**, only insofar as the **contested authority must, within a short period of time, after coordination with the corresponding ministerial portfolios implement a plan that primarily contemplates the adoption of measures aimed at the reintegration or professional retraining of affected workers, as well as the management of the creation of mechanisms to control the effective development of these measures, in order to ensure that the transition to an environmentally sustainable economy is made to the extent that the rights of workers whose labor rights have been threatened are also safeguarded.**” (Para. 11)

Conclusion drawn:

Climate Justice: Inclusive Energy Transition [Everyone Must Be on Board]

Low-income communities cannot bear a disproportionate share of the climate burden and be deprived of the benefits of the Energy Transition.

Climate Justice: Protecting Fundamental Rights + Climate Change + Environment + etc.

Climate Justice: Energy Justice + Environmental Justice

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THANK YOU!

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